
Being Human to Nature: A Call from the World of Sciences

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Abstract: This article deals with the clarion call from the contemporary sciences to “befriend” nature; they also remind us that **every human being needs to move towards being human**. The call and the reminder become serious and urgent, more than ever before, as the damages done to the earth and the environment increasingly become more severe and alarming and some of the damages are even irrevocable. Let us analyze the issue from three specific angles, in which contemporary sciences invite every human being to move towards being human: the fact of **mystery**, the need for **meaning in life** and the demand for **wisdom**.

The author expects science to collaborate with other disciplines to enrich humanity. It is high time that we realized, as Philip Clayton declares, “... science alone will never provide the answer” (Clayton, 2006: xvi). To look for meaning of life merely in scientific endeavors will be like

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looking for the right thing in a wrong place, or the wrong thing in a right place... but in both the cases, we will be the losers! *Why should we, as rational beings, who are able to develop sciences, be the losers after all?*

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Human beings of the ultramodern society are invited by the contemporary sciences to befriend nature. As the technologies develop in a very rapid manner, the life-styles change drastically, the value systems undergo a lot of changes, the ways how humans look at nature and the environment also change a lot. The changes in the outlook towards nature are unfortunately detrimental to it, and that, in turn, affects not only humans but also all living creatures and the whole of the environment. This article, given this scenario, deals with the clarion call from the contemporary sciences to “befriend” nature; they also remind us that **every human being needs to move towards being human**. The call and the reminder become serious and urgent, more than ever before, as the damages done to the earth and the environment increasingly become more severe and alarming and some of the damages are even irrevocable. Let us analyze the issue from three specific angles, in which contemporary sciences invite every human being to move towards being human: the fact of **MYSTERY**, the need for **MEANING IN LIFE** and the demand for **WISDOM**.

Interconnectedness in Nature

There is a very burning need to befriend the earth and the environment. When I say that we need to befriend nature, I don't mean at all that nature is always hostile to us, nor that we are strangers to it. In fact, we all are very much part of nature. The inter-connectedness between us and nature is so much that, it is said, about fifty minerals, salts and chemical elements, like iron, carbon, oxygen, calcium, potassium, magnesium, iodine

etc., that are in our bodies are also abundantly found in nature, in plants, animals, insects and even in the distant stars, millions and billions of light years away. As we are very much part of nature, the mother earth, for instance, does not reject us when we are buried after we die, nor the atmosphere rejects the smoke that comes out when our bodies are burnt.

All these chemicals and minerals have to be in our body at right quantities and ratio. It is astounding to realize that all these minerals and chemicals are lifeless in themselves but are very essential for us to have life! For instance, the presence of iron in our body – we all know that iron is very necessary for blood production. Nearly 70 % of the body's iron is available in the red blood cells (hemoglobin) and in muscle cells (myoglobin). This hemoglobin does the job of transferring oxygen in the blood from the lungs to the tissues. The presence of the required amount of iron in our body is very important. The deficiency of iron (anemia) causes several bad effects in us like, unusual tiredness (fatigue), paleness, shortness of breath, headaches and dizziness, heart palpitations, dry/damaged hair and skin, swelling and soreness of tongue and mouth, restless leg syndrome (i.e., a strong urge to move the legs when at rest), brittle/spoon-shaped nails, craving for some types of food, feeling anxious, cold hands and feet, more frequent infections and so on. Similarly, the need and the importance of phosphorus in our body is indeed very significant – it builds strong teeth, it is responsible in controlling the mechanism of how our body stores and uses energy up, it helps in reducing muscle pain after exercises, it is important for the process of filtering out waste in our kidneys, it helps to grow, maintain, and repair tissues and cells all over the body, it is helpful in producing DNA and RNA, the genetic building blocks of life. If the amount of phosphorus in our body is less than the required amount it causes bone diseases such as rickets (in children) and osteomalacia (in adults). If there is an improper balance of phosphorus and calcium it may lead to cause osteoporosis.

We are, thus, very much part of nature and nature is part of us. We cannot but be friends to nature. Of course, sometimes when we are struck by natural disasters like earthquakes, floods or tsunamis, we tend to think that nature works out against our survival and well-being. But in many of such cases it can be traced out that nature, in its efforts to maintain its own fine balance, just reacts to our actions; so these natural disasters can be seen just reactions of nature to our actions, which are very often highly detrimental to nature. For instance, at present (May 2020) the whole world is greatly challenged by the invisible (and invincible as of now!) enemy of Covid19. More than 200 countries in the world face the brunt of this alarming threat by this virus; more than 200, 000 have unfortunately lost their lives and more than three million have been affected by this virus; our deep sympathy to those suffering in one way or the other; heartfelt condolences to those who have lost their dear and near ones; sincere prayers that those who died may find the Eternal Rest and hearty appreciation to those who work day and night to cure the affected, to curb the spread of the disease and to find out the vaccine. On the other hand, nature seems to be breathing with ease these days, with less pollution in the air and water; the Mount Everest easily visible from Punjab, a few hundreds of KM away, which was not so earlier, due to heavy pollution in the air; the river Yamuna is cleaner; about one million square KM of hole in the Ozone layer has healed itself. All these remind us that we need to rethink about life-styles and priorities in life. In fact, when we take care of the environment we actually take care of ourselves indirectly!

Needless to say that nature sustains all sorts of lives on the earth – microbes, insects, plants and animals, including humans. It is sheer arrogance (or ignorance!) on our part to think that we, as human beings, have special rights over the natural environment compared to other creatures. The earth has been, and continues to be, a comfortable home and a safe haven for millions and millions types of creatures. Every creature has a right for safe its living on this planet earth. The tendency to demand that humans have more

rights over the natural environment is known as “speciesism” – this idea was first introduced by the English philosopher Richard Ryder (1970s) and later developed by the Australian philosopher Peter Singer. Speciesism is basically a type of discrimination based on species membership; it tries to treat members of one species as morally more significant than members of other species, even when their interests are equivalent. Going along this, humans justify that they have greater moral rights than non-human animals. This kind of attitude finds nothing wrong in killing and using other animals for humans’ well-being. Of course there is a strong inter-dependence among all the creatures; one is eaten by others to survive; the food of one creature becomes the death of another one. So it goes without saying that for our survival we obviously need to depend on plants and animals. All living beings, other than humans, moved by their instincts, are quite sober, natural and considerate in using the natural resources **ONLY** for their survival and sustenance. For instance, an elephant does not generally destroy sugarcane plants or banana trees, unless it goes berserk! When it eats leaves, it eats as much as it can and leaves the other leaves untouched. We don’t find greediness among the animal kingdom and they take from nature just what they need for their survival. Some ‘intelligent’ creatures may store for future, but not for several generations to come, which only humans can do. They don’t eat for luxury, nor for pleasure, nor for taste nor for styles; unfortunately we, who claim to be the most rational and intelligent beings in the universe are doing all these three; still worse, by deliberately doing all these we spoil our health and the fine balanced fabrics of nature.

No other living being is **seen to damage and destroy the earth** and the environment as human beings have recklessly done, and are still doing; the damages are unfortunately on the increase! It is high time that we realized that rivers, oceans, forests, birds, animals, insects, microbes and so on can live without us; in fact they can even live better without us, but we can never live without them. Einstein seems to have said: *If bees disappeared*

off the face of the earth, man would only have four years left to live.” It is quite shocking; we and the whole eco-system depend on these little creatures, because the honey-bees contribute to the growth and maintenance of the plants and trees in nature by the process of pollination in the plants; if we are so fundamentally dependent on other species, and we cannot just think of surviving without them, how on earth can we justify that humans are better and more important species on the earth?

Human Being Vs Being Human!

Being born as a human being is something that has happened to us, we have not chosen or worked for that; but ‘being human’ is a choice that demands a radical change in our attitudes and actions. Biologically and genetically we are, no doubt, human beings, but to be emotionally, psychologically and morally human is our choice; for instance, I can choose to be an immoral person in my words, actions and attitudes. Human beings have to positively act to become human (and humane) in their dealings with one another and nature. When human beings thus become ‘human’ they automatically become wise, humble, considerate and friendly. They become aware of their own finitude and their dependency upon one another and nature for their very continued existence. How to be human towards nature? It is by befriending nature and the environment.

Science with all its recent researches, discoveries and inventions, seem to teach us that it is not enough that we are human beings, but we need to learn how to be human (and humane). We need to learn from science how to be human. Being human involves, among many other, being humble to learn, being considerate to live and let live, and above all, to be responsible in protecting nature and the environment, because, as the most rational beings of all the known creatures in the universe, we have the utmost duty and we are morally bound to save the earth for our future generations.

The modern philosophy of science makes us realize that that

science cannot be value-neutral but value-bound. Value-based science is the need of the hour, as the value-neutral science can easily lead us to self-destruction. Contemporary sciences force us to revisit our very concept of science; it demands us to be wise, not otherwise.

I like to approach the call of contemporary science to 'be human' from three specific angles: the roles played by *Mystery*, *Meaning* and *Wisdom* in contemporary science.

The Fact of MYSTERY

Contemporary science questions the classical understanding of 'reality'. The new discoveries and observations, both in the macro and the micro worlds, challenge the dogmas of scientism and they "radically alter the status of knowledge and the place of the knowing subject" (Magnin, 2006: 140). *The mysterious nature of matter*: Heisenberg's principle of uncertainty and Bohr's principle of complementarity suggest that the actual nature of reality escapes our complete understanding, because, "The elementary particle is neither a wave nor a corpuscle but a 'thing' that combines the two images" (Magnin, 2006: 146). Therefore, at that level, matter ceases to be 'material' and "Matter has lost its substance" (Thuan, 2006: 181). *The Mystery of the 'Fine-tuning'*: The study of biotic coincidences and the anthropic principles seems to suggest that the universe has been very meticulously fine-tuned to be ready to receive conscious human beings; being convinced of this Freeman Dyson asserts that "the universe knew we were coming" (Dyson, 1979: 250) and Paul Davies declares that "We are truly meant to be here" (Davies, 1992: 232). Fine-tuning in the universe, though may not be a proof, but a strong indicator for an intelligent design behind the universe; for instance, the initial density of the universe had to be meticulously fixed to an accuracy of 10^{-60} and this precision is like an archer hitting a one-centimeter-square target placed fifteen billion light-years away (Thuan, 2006: 184). Several scientists-turned theologians, like John Polkinghorne, Arthur Peacock, Ilya Prigogine etc. also find something more to the evolution process

than mere chance. They have gone beyond reductionism and are open to mystical and metaphysical overtones in their approach to reality. Even great minds, like Einstein, are also convinced that such fine-tuning in the universe cannot be the outcome of a mere chance.

If one argues that all these fine-tunings are just fixed by laws of physics, then the question arises: “Where do the laws of physics come from? And why *those* laws rather than some other set?” (Davies, 2006: 31). Therefore, the mystery still remains! Such a realization of mystery in nature makes the investigation of the universe meaningful and thereby gives meaning to for our existence.

The Need for MEANING IN LIFE

One of the fundamental ways to define humans is to see them as ‘seekers of meaning’. As Victor Frankl shows, the search for ‘meaning in life’ becomes more fundamental to life than food, shelter and clothing; for, even if one has enough food, shelter and clothing, one cannot still manage to live, if one does not have meaning in life. Philip Clayton shows that the meaning-quest is related to the very nature of human being and sciences alone will not be sufficient to comprehend human nature, and therefore, the quest for meaning cannot be satisfactorily fulfilled by science alone, though science may contribute something in the process of meaning-seeking.

Though humans are biologically very much a part of creation and share a lot with other creatures, yet they seem to be far different from all of them, in terms of reason, will power, ability to imagine, the exercise of control over natural passion and above all the ability to go beyond the immediate environment. However, we cannot easily define life, nor its meaning or purpose, ***because the “questioner” and the “questioned” are one and the same here.*** Modern neuroscience may succeed in mapping the areas of the brain to find out what happens when one is filled with love or hatred, fear or tranquility; Psychology may come up with

convincing theories about the good effects of love and the bad effects due to its absence. ***But science cannot exactly define what love is, and since it is this love that makes one find meaning in life, science can comprehend neither love nor meaning.***

The Demand for WISDOM

As science proceeds we realize that we lose our grip over reality. The classical notions of certainty, causality, absolute measurability and stability are significantly challenged today. We are forced to get reconciled with arbitrary nature of the initial conditions, irreducibility, uncertainty, and unpredictability. By this “we are reminded of the contingency and finite nature of man” (Magnin, 2006: 142). Such realization of our finitude makes us wise and humble. We are cautioned not to meddle with the wisdom of nature that has been there for about fourteen billion years.

If we lose the sense of mystery, if we are not able to find meaning in our existence, and if we don't become wise enough not to ignore the place of values in science, we will have to face the doom of humanity. As Francis Bacon wished science must take us back to the glorious state of pre-fallen state. It should make us wise, not otherwise; unless we are smart and humble enough to learn from nature, nature will teach us some certain things in a hard way. Science is like a sword, having sharp ends on both sides and unless we are careful, we may end up using science as a tool of desolation and it would be like chopping off the very branch of the tree upon which we are sitting. In fact, Claude Levi Strauss cautions us that “the world began without the human being, and will end without him” (Levi-Strauss 1955).

Conclusion

A revised understanding of science, that is, science with the human face, will surely enrich humanity. Enriching humanity would mean, among many other things, making humans more sensible to mysteries, enabling them to find more meaning in their

existence and wiser. Though humans have enormous cognitive power, yet they are cosmically very insignificant in the vast dark universe, known and unknown. As Blasé Pascal has it, “Man is only a reed, more frail than nature, but he is a thinking reed. It does not need the whole universe to wipe him out; a breath, a drop of water, is enough to kill him...” But still humans are more powerful and noble than the universe, because, “he knows that he dies and knows the advantage the universe has over him” (Pascal, 1976: 231 & 145), whereas the universe that kills him does not, cannot know anything.

With due admiration and respect to science, we dearly expect science to collaborate with other disciplines to enrich humanity. It is high time that we realized, as Philip Clayton declares, “... science alone will never provide the answer” (Clayton, 2006: xvi). To look for meaning of life merely in scientific endeavors will be like looking for the right thing in a wrong place, or the wrong thing in a right place... but in both the cases, we will be the losers! *Why should we, as rational beings, who are able to develop sciences, be the losers after all?*

Notes

1. However, from the religious perspectives one may argue that humans are the climax of all creations and they have been created in the image and likeness of God. One may quote the book of Genesis in the Bible that God allowed humans to subdue the whole earth and to have dominion over it; but the scripture scholars seek to interpret that powerful dominion as responsible stewardship, which invites humans to be co-creators with God, in preserving and enriching nature. Genesis 2:15 says, “Then the LORD God took the man and put him into the garden of Eden to cultivate it and keep it”; this makes it clear that human beings must be responsible to take care of it, not to dominate and destroy it for selfish purposes. Be that as it may, but from the nature’s point of view, humans are one among the millions and millions of creatures in the world, though they are the only self-conscious beings.

2. See: https://www.vice.com/en_in/article/d7ezaq/what-would-happen-if-all-the-bees-died-tomorrow. Accessed on 4 May, 2020
3. Of course, from religious and faith perspectives one may say that God has a great plan from eternity that I am born and he knows even before I am formed in the womb of my mother. But still one might argue that I did not actually make any choice to be born!
4. For details see: <http://www.inquiriesjournal.com/articles/660/viktor-frankls-logotherapy-the-search-for-purpose-and-meaning>. Accessed on 4 May, 2020.
5. See: <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/view/19108279/science-and-the-search-for-meaning-philip-clayton>. Accessed on 4 May, 2020.
6. In spite of all these special and unique features, in terms of sharing the earth's resources we cannot easily justify that we have more rights than the other creatures, as we discussed above.

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“I recognize that globalization has helped many people rise out of poverty, but it has also damned many others to starve to death. It is true that global wealth is growing in absolute terms, but inequalities have also grown and new poverty arisen.- Pope Francis

“When money, instead of man, is at the center of the system, when money becomes an idol, men and women are reduced to simple instruments of a social and economic system, which is characterized, better yet dominated, by profound inequalities. So we discard whatever is not useful to this logic; it is this attitude that discards children and older people, and is now affecting the young.” -Pope Francis